

Shift the Paradigm of Composites Modeling with AI

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“for foundational discoveries and inventions
that enable machine learning
with artificial neural networks”

THE ROYAL SWEDISH ACADEMY OF SCIENCES

Is Physics-based Modeling Still Needed?

Tycho Brahe
(1546-1601)

Astronomical & Planetary
Observations (Data)

Johannes Kepler
(1571-1630)

Laws of Planetary Motion
(Curve Fitting)

Isaac Newton
(1642-1726)

Laws of Motion & Gravitation
(Modeling)

Challenges: Multiscale/Anisotropy/Heterogeneity

1 mm³ material block ~ **20 Million** DOFs

MSG: A top-down modeling framework that *models relevant behavior in terms of microstructural details as needed and affordable.*

SwiftComp™

A Purdue Technology

Principle of Minimum Information Loss

- Virtual testing of materials/structures
 - Mechanical properties
 - Multifunctional properties
 - Transport properties
- Multiscale modeling of structures
 - Composite structures
 - Stiffened structures
 - Build-up structures
 - Sandwich structures

MSG-based Progressive Damage Analysis for Composites

Progressive Damage Analysis of Open-hole Laminate

- Material: IM7/8552 laminate
- Layup: $[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$
- Dimensions: 300 x 38 mm hole diameter 6.35mm
- Mesh: 11800 quad elements
- Material properties:

(a) Lamina elastic properties

E_1	$E_2 = E_3$	$G_{12} = G_{13}$	G_{23}	$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	ν_{23}
171.42 GPa	9.08 GPa	5.29 GPa	4.27 GPa	0.32	0.45

(b) Strength properties (MPa)

X^T	X^C	$Y^T = Z^T$	$Y^C = Z^C$	$S_{12} = S_{13}$	S_{23}
2323.5	1200.1	62.3	253	92.3	107.6

(c) Fracture energy (kJ/m²)

$G_{1,c}^+$	$G_{1,c}^-$	$G_{2,c}^+ = G_{3,c}^+$	$G_{2,c}^- = G_{3,c}^-$
133.3	61	0.28	1.31

Progressive Damage Analysis of Open-hole Laminate

A: initial failure
B: ultimate failure

Damage variable d1 (a)-(d) (Left) and d2 (e)-(h) (Right) at the ultimate failure

Challenges for Composites Modeling

1. High computational costs for complex 3D microstructures
2. Idealized microstructures
3. Unknown constituent properties and constitutive models
4. Interface with other codes to form the end-to-end simulation
5. Highly specialized training (PhD level) for confidently performing composites simulations, unaffordable for small companies

AI-Assisted MSG-based Composites Modeling

1. Create ultra-efficient surrogate models
2. Produce realistic microstructures using image recognition or generation
3. Learn unknown constituent properties & constitutive models
4. Integrate different tools using human language
5. Democratize the use of simulation workflows using a domain-specific LLM

Effective Thermal Conductivity of Woven Composites

- Deep learning neural network (DNN) model
 - Include both microscale and mesoscale features
 - Mixed continuous (e.g., yarn geometries) and discrete (weave patterns) input data

DNN architecture

In-plane conductivity vs yarn width

Out-of-plane conductivity vs yarn thickness

Failure Strength Prediction of Woven Composites

➤ Data-driven yarn failure criterion

Multiscale failure analysis

Replace microscale modeling with a DNN model

Model	Xt	Xc	Zt	Zc	R	S
Two-scale MSG	149.81	294.25	39.91	144.60	22.94	19.10
DL model	148.84	295.74	39.44	140.11	22.78	19.11
Diff(MSG vs DL)	0.65%	0.51%	1.18%	3.11%	0.70%	0.05%

- Good accuracy compared with high-fidelity model
- Significantly improved efficiency

AI-Assisted MSG-based Composites Modeling

Hybrid Neural Network – Finite Element Model

➤ Train constitutive model with **indirectly** measurable data

Learn Lamina Constitutive Law Based on Laminate Response

➤ Couple neural network with Abaqus for model training

- Training data: Surface displacements
- Learned model: Stress-strain relation

Damage material stiffness matrix to be learned

CompositesAI™: AI-Powered Composites Expert System

Expert Knowledge Intelligentized in CompositesAI

how to compute the upper bound of young's modulus for a two-phase isotropic composite

CompositesAI

To compute the upper bound of Young's modulus for a two-phase isotropic composite, you generally use the Voigt rule of mixtures. The Voigt upper bound assumes isostrain conditions (i.e., the strain is uniform across the phases). For constituents with equal Poisson's ratios ($\nu_f = \nu_m$), the upper bound is given by:

$$E_V^* = V_f E_f + V_m E_m$$

where:

- E_f and E_m are the Young's moduli of the fiber and matrix (the two phases),
- V_f and V_m are their respective volume fractions.

However, if the two isotropic phases have different Poisson's ratios ($\nu_f \neq \nu_m$), the simple rule above is not the strict upper bound. In this case, the upper bound is obtained by extracting Young's modulus from the effective stiffness matrix calculated according to the Voigt rule, incorporating both moduli and Poisson's ratios. The result is always greater than the simple mixture rule due to the influence of differing Poisson's ratios.

Thus, for most accurate results, when $\nu_f \neq \nu_m$, you should compute the effective stiffness matrix using the Voigt approach and then extract the effective Young's modulus from that matrix, rather than relying solely on the simple mixture formula

Simulation via CompositesAI

➤ Integrate commercial code SwiftComp for multiscale modeling

- No need of FE knowledge
- Execute sophisticated code using natural language
- Guide the process of preparing input and understand outputs
- [Live on CompositesAI](#) (AC)

for a unidirectional fiber reinforced composites, I would like to know G_{13} and G_{23} , do you have a tool to help me compute it?

CompositesAI

Yes, I have a specialized tool that can compute the shear moduli G_{13} and G_{23} (as well as other engineering constants) for unidirectional fiber-reinforced composites. This tool requires the following inputs:

Fiber and matrix elastic properties (E , ν or full set if anisotropic)

Fiber volume fraction

Packing arrangement (e.g., hexagonal, square)

If you provide:

Fiber modulus (E_f) and Poisson's ratio (ν_f)

Matrix modulus (E_m) and Poisson's ratio (ν_m)

Fiber volume fraction (V_f)

Packing type (default is hexagonal if not specified)

I can obtain G_{13} and G_{23} for your system. Please supply the above inputs or confirm if you want to use prior examples.

isotropic fiber with $E=300$ GPa, $\nu=0.3$; isotropic matrix with $E=20$ GPa, $\nu=0.4$, hexagonal, $V_f=68\%$

CompositesAI

View Result from `homogenize_elastic_constants` ▾

For a unidirectional fiber-reinforced composite with isotropic fibers ($E_f = 300$ GPa, $\nu_f = 0.3$), isotropic matrix ($E_m = 20$ GPa, $\nu_m = 0.4$), hexagonal packing, and a fiber volume fraction of 68%, the calculated shear moduli are:

$$G_{13} = 28.86 \text{ GPa}$$

$$G_{23} = 31.58 \text{ GPa}$$

These values are computed using physics-based homogenization methods appropriate for your specified microstructure and constituent properties.

Your numbers are a bit high. Try $E_f = 231$ GPa, Poisson's ratio of the fiber is 0.35. $E_m = 4$ GPa, Poisson's ratio of matrix is 0.3.

CompositesAI

View Result from `homogenize_elastic_constants` ▾

For a unidirectional fiber-reinforced composite with the following properties:

Isotropic fiber: $E_f = 231$ GPa, $\nu_f = 0.35$

Isotropic matrix: $E_m = 4$ GPa, $\nu_m = 0.3$

Hexagonal packing, fiber volume fraction $V_f = 68\%$

The computed shear moduli are:

$$G_{13} = 7.50 \text{ GPa}$$

$$G_{23} = 7.21 \text{ GPa}$$

These values reflect a physically realistic shear response for your specified composite system.

cdmHUB Community: Experts Interact with AI

- Mission: to convene & serve the composites community by creation, education, evaluation, and sharing of resources for composites design & manufacturing
- [Live on cdmHUB Community](#)

Composites Modeling in the Era of AI

- Physics-based modeling still needed
 - Rigorously model advanced materials featuring general anisotropy and heterogeneity
 - Provide data and simulation tools for AI
- AI helps
 - Reducing computational cost
 - Creating more realistic microstructures
 - Discovering unknown physics information
 - Consolidating and delivering composites knowledge
 - Distilling experts' insights

CompositesAI.com

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